

India's Pathway To Viksit Bharat @ 2047 through Integrated Farming System

Harvir Singh Chaudhary¹ & Tanya Tyagi²

1. Associate professor, Deptt. of Economics, J.V. Jain College Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh, Email Id:- drharvirsinghchaudhary@gmail.com,
2. Scholar, MA in Economics, 3rd semester (2nd year), J.V. Jain College Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh, Email Id:- anamikatanyasre@gmail.com

Received : 05/11/2025

1st BPR : 15/11/2025

2nd BPR : 27/11/2025

Accepted : 09/12/2025

Abstract

As we know India's 2025 Global Hunger Index is 102nd out of 123 countries. India lies in serious category with 25.8 score in GHI. It show India is lagging behind other countries in nourishing the people of the country. In other reports like Human Development Report , India ranks 130th out of 193 countries with a score of 0.685 for the year 2023. It show India is lagging behind in Human Capital Formation. In this regard, Integrated Farming System play a crucial role in leveraging India's vision of 2047 through Nutrients Fortification, Climate Resilient, Sustainable Agriculture through "waste is useful" results in Doubling Farmer's income . Bring prosperity, resilience and long term growth in India's goal of Viksit Bharat.

Key words: GHI, HDR, Integrated Farming System, Climate resilience, waste is useful, Viksit Bharat, food security.

Introduction:-

India's "Viksit Bharat @ 2047" vision aims to transform the nation into a developed economy by the centenary of its independence. A critical component of this ambitious goal is the fundamental transition of the Agriculture sector. Currently, it employs over 46.1% of the workforce is central to India's economy. Despite, significant growth during the green revolution. It still , grapple with persistent challenges like fragmented landholdings, low productivity, low water table , Climate change and its impact , water scarcity and soil degradation.

Traditional monoculture practices or rice-wheat cycle practices often exacerbate these issues, leading to environmental stress and unstable Farmer's incomes. In response , Integrated Farming System (IFS) emerge as a vital , Sustainable pathway to address these multifaceted challenges. IFS is a versatile synergistic approach that integrates various farm enterprises. Such as crops , livestock, poultry , horticulture and aquaculture, on a single farm to optimize resource utilization, reduce wastage of resources through Nutrients recycling and enhance overall farm resilience.

Objectives:-

Objective of this research paper is to analyze and propose a road map for Doubling Farmer's income , swift transition of agriculture sector into a sustainable, profitable , and resilient system that ensures food security, enhance Farmer's livelihood and significantly contributes to National Development Goals(NDGs).

Another objective of this research paper is to focus on the impact of Integrated Farming System on India's Climate and different agro climatic zones of India.

One more objective is that Integrated Farming System is able to make India Viksit @ 2047 through it's integrated and synergistic approach of Farming.

Methodology:-

The study is based on literature and looks into the present topic. We also relied on secondary data from economic survey (2024-25) , journals and legitimate websites of various organizations.

Hypothesis :-

H1- Impact of Integrated Farming System on Climate resilience and environmental sustainability.

H2- Impact of Integrated Farming System on Doubling the Farmer's income.

Literature Review:-

The academic literature highlights the significant potential of Integrated Farming System in transitioning Indian Agriculture and achieving the broader goals of Viksit Bharat @ 2047 . Research across the country has consistently demonstrated that multi-component farming systems are more effective than sole cropping in fulfilling diverse demands , ensuring nutritional security and preserving environmental sustainability.

Diagram with Explanation

- On a same piece of land , various activities are practiced through integrated farming system.
- This picture represent waste is useful .
- Through animal and plant waste a slurry is prepared through biogas plant.
- That slurry is used as a manure in soil to provide fertility and regenerate organic contents of the soil.
- Crop produced from the soil is used to feed livestock and cattle.
- With rice crop , aquaculture is also done to use water effectively and sustainably.
- Then , fishes are sold for commercial sale with crops.
- As a result, a virtuous cycle would be created for Doubling the Farmer's income.

Advantages of Integrated Farming System

- Increase Productivity of the system : Due to the intensification of crop and allied enterprises economic yield / unit area per unit time increases.
- Increase Profitability: The cost of production declines and but income increases.
- Improve Potentiality / sustainability : Through effective recycling of linked components as manure , it is possible to sustain the production base.
- Provide balanced food : cereals, vegetables, fruits , fish , non- veg etc.
- Encourage recycling of byproducts : Product / waste material is used as input to another mushroom- the cost of production reduced.
- Avail money round the year : farmers income from cereals , vegetable , fruit , non-veg , poultry etc. round the year.
- Solve the energy crisis : use of fossil fuel would be limited. Use of biogas etc. Production.
- Solve fodder problems: Fodder crops are grown and parts of others may be used.
- Avoid degradation of forests : Wide gap exists in demand and availability of fuel wood and timber and still increasing. IFS may help.
- Employment generation : more laborers required in IFS. Round the year requirement.
- Provide the opportunity for agro-based industries : Side industries may be developed.

- Increase input efficiency : Farm resources are used more effectively and helped in increased benefit-cost ratio.
- Improves standard of living of the farmer : Availability of cereals, vegetable, fruit , non-veg. , poultry, fish , mushroom etc. round the year improves economic status and standard of living.

Issues-

But there are some roadblocks in this pathway due to monotonic preference of rice wheat cycle. And , over-dependence on crops like sugarcane which are not only water guzzling crops. But also through these cropping patterns , we are harming our water ground level. In states like Punjab , Haryana , Western Uttar Pradesh and others , in excess quantity use of fertilizers . Urea is heavily dominant in use for nitrogen which further exaggerate demand for water. As a result , water ground level kept on falling day by day . India imports Urea in huge quantity from other countries. It also impact India's trade deficit . As well as , Government of India, provide huge amount of subsidies in the context of fertilizers through schemes like PM-PRANAM (Pradhan Mantri Programme for Restoration, Awareness Generation, Nourishment, and Amelioration of Mother-Earth). Due to which , government's fiscal deficit also increases . Through these exports we not only export crops but also our water. India is at top in the production of rice . India is at top in the production of sugarcane. India is at third position in the production of wheat. This can be explained with the help of tables in which data is taken from renowned organizations websites.

Top Rice Producing Countries in the World

Countries with their position in the world.	%(percentage) of global production.	Total production (2024/2025 in metric tonnes).
1.India	28	150 million
2.China	27	145.28 million
3.Bangladesh	7	36.6 million
4.Indonesia	6	34.1 million
5.Vietnam	5	26.75 million
6.Thailand	4	20.55 million
7.Philippines	2	12.37 million
8.Myanmar	2	11.9 million
9.Pakistan	2	9.72 million
10.Brazil	2	8.68 million

Source : USDA (US Department of Agriculture)

Top Rice Producing Countries in the World (Share %)

Source : USDA

Top Sugarcane Producing Countries in the World

Countries with their position in the world.	%(percentage) of global production.	Total production (2024/2025 in metric tonnes).
1.Brazil	24	43.7 million
2.India	15	28 million
3.European Union	9	16.5 million
4.China	6	11 million
5.Thailand	6	10.04 million
6.United States	5	8.45 million
7.Russia	4	6.5 million
8.Pakistan	3	5.86 million
9.Mexico	3	5.1 million
10.Australia	2	3.85 million

Source : USDA (US Department of Agriculture)

Top Wheat Producing Countries in the World

Countries with their position in the world.	%(percentage) of global production.	Total production (2024/2025 in metric tonnes).
1.China	17	140.1 million
2.European Union	15	122.15 million
3.India	14	113.29 million
4.Russia	10	81.6 million
5.United States of America	7	53.85 million
6.Canada	4	35.94 million
7.Australia	4	34.11 million
8.Pakistan	4	31.44 million
9.Ukraine	3	23.4 million
10.Turkey	2	19 million

Source : USDA (US Department of Agriculture)

Source : USDA

Suggestions

India's farmer should focus on other sunrise sectors like floriculture, Aquaculture, Horticulture, and livestock. In these sectors, foreign demand is very high. India is a major producer of shrills especially Andhra Pradesh. These sectors help in Doubling the Farmer's income (2016 GOI goal).

As we know, 2023- was celebrated as the International Millet Of the Year . India is a major producer of millet with 38.4% according to 2023 report of FAO. India is the 5th largest exporter of millets according to February, 2022 (data of PIB) in the world. India can increase the production of these crops as they are Climate Resilient and water deficient crops. Their demand in the world market rising significantly due to health and sustainability trends.

Various Schemes Introduced by Government of India

Government of India introduced many schemes in this regard to suffice and propagate India's pathway to Vision @ 20247 by DOUBLING THE FARMER'S INCOME. Schemes like PM-DDKY (Pradhan Mantri Dhan Dhanya Krishi Yojana) an umbrella scheme which covers many other 36 Agriculture related schemes with 11 ministries of Government of India , PM-KISAN (Pradhan Mantri Kisan Samman Nidhi) provides Rs.6000/- to farmers in three installments in a year, PM- KSY (Krishi Sinchaiyee Yojana) (Per Drop More Crop) ensures protective irrigation to farmer's farm , PM-FBY (Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana) provides insurance coverage due to natural failures or disasters, KCC (Kisan Credit Card) scheme provides affordable credit at reasonable rate of interest , SHC (Soil Health Card) scheme provides essential information to farmer about the condition of the farmer's farm soil , NPOF (National Project on Organic Farming) promotes organic inputs and practices , NLM (National Livestock Mission) promotes livestock development and entrepreneurship and other schemes.

Conclusion

IFS is a vital , sustainable and synergistic approach essential for transforming Indian Agriculture into a resilient, self reliant and economically viable and robust sector of a developed nation by 2047. The strategy recognises that strengthening local food Systems through integrated farming system is indispensable to national progress , especially as small and marginal farmers , who make up 85 % of India's total workforce of agrarian economy , are central to India's rural livelihood and food security. Empowering these farmers through robust , decentralized or democratized or localized Food Systems does not merely serve agricultural advancement - it is pivotal to realising the goal of Viksit Bharat @ 2047 vision.

Agriculture at a glance: Current status and 2047 alignment

Key performance metrics highlight how India's farm sector is progressing, and where it connects with the government's long-term vision.

Table with 3 columns and 10 rows. (column headers with buttons are sortable)			
	Category	Current status	Viksit Bharat 2047 alignment
1	Small farmers' share	85 per cent of farmers (owning <2 ha)	Self-reliance through small farmer empowerment
2	Agricultural growth rate	5 per cent annually (2017-2023)	Sustainable agricultural growth target
3	Food production (2024-25)	353.96 million tonnes	Food security for 1.6 billion population
4	PM-KISAN coverage	Over 110 million farmers	Direct income support for rural prosperity
5	Agricultural credit access for small farmers	76 per cent (up from 57 per cent in 2014-15)	Financial inclusion for marginalised farmers

Table with 3 columns and 10 rows. (column headers with buttons are sortable)

	Category	Current status	Viksit Bharat 2047 alignment
6	Lakshpati Didis target	30 million women by 2047	Women empowerment in rural economy
7	Rural employment (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act)	2,500+ million person-days annually	Rural employment generation, assist and capacity creation
8	Productivity increase for rice	19.29 per cent increase (2013-24)	Productivity enhancement goals
9	Productivity increase for wheat	13.16 per cent increase (2013-24)	Staple food and nutrition security targets
10	Productivity increase for coarse cereals	71.52 per cent increase (2013-24)	Nutritional security through crop diversity and resilience

Source : down to earth.

References

- Inspira journals.com – Viksit Bharat @ 2047 :- Pathway to Sustainable Agriculture Development in India.
- Mosaic India - Integrated Farming System: A Sustainable Model for Indian Agriculture.
- www.pib.gov.in
- www.globalhungerindex.org
- www.hdwww.hd.org
- Economic survey (2024-2025), CH- AGRICULTURE AND FOOD MANAGEMENT: THE SECTOR OF THE FUTURE .
- www.usad.com
- CEEW Research- what are Integrated Farming Systems in India?
- www.unfao.com
- Department of Agriculture and Farmers welfare - www.agriwelfare.gov.in
- www.downtoearth.org.in

*** **